

COUPLING BETWEEN SUBMERGED, VERTICALLY ALIGNED LOOP ANTENNAS

Dr. Gene E. Layman

Naval Research Laboratory
Washington, D.C. 20375

Abstract

This paper presents the derivation of a closed form solution for the coupling between vertically aligned, coplanar loop antennas located within a conductive half space. The formal solution to this problem is expressed as a complex integral equation for which there is no known solution. Previous approximations have been constrained to special cases (e.g., large distances between antenna, neither antenna near the surface). The author develops approximations within the integrand that allows an accurate solution to be found for any combination of antenna depths, including one antenna located at the surface.

Introduction

There are two methods that are normally used to determine the field strength within a conductive half space resulting from simple radiating antennas placed within that medium. The first, and simplest, method is to assume total reflection at the boundary, replace the second medium with an image antenna (the familiar image antenna approach), and sum the fields from the two antennas. While very useful in general, this approach is inadequate in certain analysis (e.g., either antenna near the boundary, radial separation much greater than antenna depths, determining the location and magnitude of antenna pattern nulls, etc.). A second and more rigorous method is to utilize the approach first formulated by Sommerfeld¹ who examined the boundary value problem of fields radiating from an electric dipole antenna located above a conductive half space. Sommerfeld expressed the solution as a set of complex integral equations that are unsolvable in closed form.

Figure 1 shows the communication configuration between coplanar loops in the form of a transmitting loop at a depth of $-z_0$ with the axis parallel to the x coordinate. The resulting magnetic field strength is determined for all points located on the negative z axis. The coplanar arrangement is preferred for communicating between loop antennas within a conductive medium. Although a coaxial orientation provides up to 6 dB gain over coplanar loops at very low frequencies, a coplanar loop orientation operating near the optimum frequency (maximum transfer of power) is best by a 7.2 dB margin.²

Wait and Campbell³ have provided a formal solution to the boundary value problem of a small loop antenna located within a conductive medium based on the original Sommerfeld method. The magnetic Hertz vector, $\bar{\Pi}_m$, from which the magnetic field may be derived, is expressed in rectangular coordinate components (Π_{mx} , Π_{my} , Π_{mz}) to describe magnitudes at points located in cylindrical coordinates (ρ , ϕ , z).

$$\Pi_{mx} = \frac{IA}{4\pi} \int_0^\infty J_0(\rho u) \left[e^{-(u^2 + \gamma_1^2)^{1/2} |z_0 - z|} + \frac{\gamma_0^2 (u^2 + \gamma_1^2)^{1/2} - \gamma_1^2 (u^2 + \gamma_0^2)^{1/2}}{\gamma_0^2 (u^2 + \gamma_1^2)^{1/2} + \gamma_1^2 (u^2 + \gamma_0^2)^{1/2}} e^{(u^2 + \gamma_1^2)^{1/2} (z + z_0)} \right]$$

Figure 1 – Vertical aligned coplanar loop antennas

$$\times \frac{u}{(u^2 + \gamma_1^2)^{1/2}} du ; \quad z \leq 0, z_0 \leq 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\Pi_{mz} = \frac{IA}{2\pi} \cos \phi \int_0^\infty J_1(\rho u) \frac{(u^2 + \gamma_1^2)^{1/2} - (u^2 + \gamma_0^2)^{1/2}}{\gamma_0^2 (u^2 + \gamma_1^2)^{1/2} + \gamma_1^2 (u^2 + \gamma_0^2)^{1/2}} \times e^{(u^2 + \gamma_1^2)^{1/2} (z + z_0)} u^2 du ; \quad z \leq 0, z_0 \leq 0 \quad (2)$$

where:

- Π_{mx}, Π_{mz} = x and z components of the magnetic Hertz vector
- ρ, ϕ, z = cylindrical coordinates
- I = loop current
- A = loop area
- z_0 = antenna depth
- γ_0, γ_1 = intrinsic propagation constant of air and conductive medium, $(-\omega^2 \mu \epsilon_0)^{1/2}$ and $(j\omega \mu \sigma - \omega^2 \mu \epsilon)^{1/2}$ respectively
- J_0, J_1 = zero and first order Bessel functions
- u = parameter of integration

At locations along the z axis the parameter ρ is zero making the z component of the magnetic Hertz vector, expressed by Eq. (2), vanish since $J_1(0) = 0$. The remaining expression, Eq. (1), may be rearranged in a manner to provide a partial solution.

$$\Pi_{mx} = \frac{IA}{4\pi} \int_0^\infty J_0(\rho\omega) \left[e^{-(u^2+\gamma_0^2)^{1/2}z_0-z} - e^{-(u^2+\gamma_1^2)^{1/2}z_0+z} \right. \\ \left. + \frac{2\gamma_0^2(u^2+\gamma_1^2)^{1/2}}{\gamma_0^2(u^2+\gamma_1^2)^{1/2} + \gamma_1^2(u^2+\gamma_0^2)^{1/2}} e^{-(u^2+\gamma_1^2)^{1/2}z_0+z} \right] \\ \times \frac{u}{u^2+\gamma_1^2} du; \quad z \leq 0, z_0 \leq 0 \quad (3)$$

The well known Sommerfeld Integral may be used to solve the integration of part of Eq. (3) containing the first two exponential functions, i.e.:

$$\frac{e^{-\gamma_1 r}}{r} = \int_0^\infty \frac{u}{(u^2+\gamma_1^2)^{1/2}} J_0(\rho u) e^{-(u^2+\gamma_1^2)^{1/2}z} du \quad (4)$$

where: $r = (\rho^2 + z^2)^{1/2}$

Using this solution by replacing $|z|$ by $|z_0 - z|$ and $|z_0 + z|$, Eq. (3) may be reduced to

$$\Pi_{mx} = \frac{IA}{4\pi} \left[\frac{e^{-\gamma_1 R_p}}{R_p} - \frac{e^{-\gamma_1 R_l}}{R_l} \right. \\ \left. + \int_0^\infty \frac{2\gamma_0^2 u J_0(\rho u) e^{-(u^2+\gamma_1^2)^{1/2}z_0+z}}{\gamma_0^2(u^2+\gamma_1^2)^{1/2} + \gamma_1^2(u^2+\gamma_0^2)^{1/2}} du \right] \quad (5)$$

where: $R_p = [\rho^2 + (z_0 - z)^2]^{1/2}$

$R_l = [\rho^2 + (z_0 + z)^2]^{1/2}$

R_p and R_l represent the distance from the observation point to the primary antenna and image antenna locations respectively. Equation (5) can be reduced to the image antenna solution approach by ignoring the contribution of the integral term.

To solve Eq. (5) for the magnetic Hertz vector along the vertical line bisecting the transmitting loop requires setting $\rho = 0$. Since $J_0(0) = 1$, this becomes:

$$\Pi_{mx} = \frac{IA}{4\pi} \left[\frac{e^{-\gamma_1|z_0-z|}}{|z_0-z|} - \frac{e^{-\gamma_1|z_0+z|}}{|z_0+z|} + \int_0^\infty \frac{2\gamma_0^2 u e^{-(u^2+\gamma_1^2)^{1/2}z_0+z}}{\gamma_0^2(u^2+\gamma_1^2)^{1/2} + \gamma_1^2(u^2+\gamma_0^2)^{1/2}} du \right] \quad (6)$$

(note: all remaining expressions are for $\rho = 0$)

Although simplified, the integral expressed in Eq. (6) is not solvable in closed form.

Solving the Integration

In order to develop the approximation to the integral in Eq. (6), it is first necessary to examine the intrinsic propagation constants for air and conductive media. At frequencies at which $\omega \epsilon \ll \sigma$ the intrinsic propagation constant for a conductive medium is generally approximated as:

$$\gamma_1 \doteq (j\omega\mu\sigma)^{1/2} \quad (7)$$

Sea water has a conductivity of about 5 mhos/meter and a relative dielectric constant of 80 (i.e., $\epsilon = \epsilon_r \epsilon_0 = 80 \times 10^{-9}/36\pi$). For sea water, $\omega \epsilon = \sigma$ at a frequency of 1.1×10^9 Hertz. Ramo, Whinnery, and Van Duzer⁴ list the frequency at which $\omega \epsilon = \sigma$ for wet and dry earth at 1.8 Megahertz and 3.8 Megahertz respectively. Since communication is practical through conductive media only at frequencies much lower than these, where $\sigma \gg \omega \epsilon$, it is possible to find a value G such that

$$|\gamma_0| \ll G \ll |\gamma_1|. \quad (8)$$

With these conditions the following approximations may be made:

$$(u^2 + \gamma_0^2)^{1/2} \doteq u \quad u \geq G \\ (u^2 + \gamma_1^2)^{1/2} \doteq \gamma_1 \quad u \leq G$$

Making these substitutions, the integral term from Eq. (6) may be approximated as:

$$INT = \frac{IA}{2\pi} \int_0^G \frac{\gamma_0^2 u e^{-\gamma_1|z_0+z|}}{\gamma_0^2 \gamma_1 + \gamma_1^2 (u^2 + \gamma_0^2)^{1/2}} \\ + \int_G^\infty \frac{\gamma_0^2 u e^{-(u^2+\gamma_1^2)^{1/2}z_0+z}}{\gamma_0^2 (u^2 + \gamma_1^2)^{1/2} + \gamma_1^2 u} \\ = \frac{IA}{2\pi} [INT_1 + INT_2] \quad (9)$$

Consider the first integral:

$$INT_1 = e^{-\gamma_1|z_0+z|} \int_0^G \frac{u}{\gamma_1 + \frac{\gamma_1^2}{\gamma_0} (u^2 + \gamma_0^2)^{1/2}} du \quad (10)$$

This integral has the solution:

$$INT_1 = e^{-\gamma_1|z_0+z|} \left[\frac{\gamma_0^2}{\gamma_1^2} (G^2 + \gamma_0^2)^{1/2} - \frac{\gamma_0^3}{\gamma_1^2} - \frac{\gamma_0^4}{\gamma_1^3} \right. \\ \left. \times \ln \left[\frac{\gamma_1 + \frac{\gamma_1^2}{\gamma_0} (G^2 + \gamma_0^2)^{1/2}}{\gamma_1 + \frac{\gamma_1^2}{\gamma_0}} \right] \right] \quad (11)$$

But $(G^2 + \gamma_0^2)^{1/2} \doteq G$, therefore

$$INT_1 \doteq e^{-\gamma_1|z_0+z|} \left[\frac{\gamma_0^2}{\gamma_1^2} G - \frac{\gamma_0^3}{\gamma_1^2} - \frac{\gamma_0^4}{\gamma_1^3} \ln \left[\frac{\gamma_0^2 + \gamma_1^2 G}{\gamma_0^2 + \gamma_1 \gamma_0} \right] \right] \quad (12)$$

And since $\gamma_1 \gg G \gg \gamma_0$, the third term within the brackets may be reduced.

$$INT_1 \doteq e^{-\gamma_1|z_0+z|} \left[\frac{\gamma_0^2}{\gamma_1^2} \left(G - \frac{\gamma_0^2}{\gamma_1} \ln \frac{G}{\gamma_0} \right) - \frac{\gamma_0^3}{\gamma_1^2} \right] \quad (13)$$

This equation may be further simplified by noting that since $G > |\gamma_0|$ then:

$$\left| \ln \frac{G}{\gamma_0} \right| < \left| \frac{G}{\gamma_0} \right|$$

Therefore:

$$\left| \frac{\gamma_0^2}{\gamma_1} \ln \frac{G}{\gamma_0} \right| < \left| \frac{\gamma_0}{\gamma_1} G \right| \ll G \quad (14)$$

And finally INT_1 may be approximated as:

$$INT_1 \doteq e^{-\gamma_1|z_0+z|} \left[\frac{\gamma_0^2}{\gamma_1^2} G - \frac{\gamma_0^3}{\gamma_1^2} \right] \quad (15)$$

From (9),

$$INT_2 = \int_G^\infty \frac{\gamma_0^2 u e^{-(u^2+\gamma_1^2)^{1/2}z_0+z}}{\gamma_0^2 (u^2 + \gamma_1^2)^{1/2} + \gamma_1^2 u} du \quad (16)$$

Notice that $\gamma_1^2 u \gg \gamma_0^2 (u^2 + \gamma_1^2)^{1/2}$ for $G \leq u < \infty$ (See (8)). At large values of u :

$$\gamma_0^2 (u^2 + \gamma_1^2)^{1/2} \doteq \gamma_0^2 u \ll \gamma_1^2 u$$

For small values of u (let $u = G$):

$$\gamma_0^2 (G^2 + \gamma_1^2)^{1/2} \doteq \gamma_0^2 \gamma_1 \ll \gamma_1^2 G$$

and:

$$\gamma_0^2 (G^2 + \gamma_1^2)^{1/2} + \gamma_1^2 u \doteq \gamma_1^2 u$$

The integral of Eq. (16) may be approximated by:

$$INT_2 \doteq \int_G^\infty \frac{\gamma_0^2}{\gamma_1^2} e^{-(u^2 + \gamma_1^2)^{1/2} z_0 + z} du \quad (17)$$

There is a definite solution for an integral that has a similar form to Eq. (17).⁵

$$\int_0^\infty \frac{e^{-(u^2 + \gamma_1^2)^{1/2} z_0 + z}}{(u^2 + \gamma_1^2)^{1/2}} du = K_0(\gamma_1 |z_0 + z|) \quad (18)$$

Where K_0 is the modified Bessel function of the second kind of zero order.

By taking a derivative with respect to z , Eq. (18) becomes:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial z} \int_0^\infty \frac{e^{-(u^2 + \gamma_1^2)^{1/2} z_0 + z}}{(u^2 + \gamma_1^2)^{1/2}} du = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} K_0(\gamma_1 |z_0 + z|) \quad (19)$$

Taking the derivative of the Bessel function yields the solution:

$$\int_0^\infty e^{-(u^2 + \gamma_1^2)^{1/2} z_0 + z} du = \gamma_1 K_1(\gamma_1 |z_0 + z|) \quad (20)$$

Thus INT_2 may be expressed as the sum of two integrals:

$$INT_2 \doteq \frac{\gamma_0^2}{\gamma_1^2} \left[\int_0^\infty e^{-(u^2 + \gamma_1^2)^{1/2} z_0 + z} du - \int_0^G e^{-(u^2 + \gamma_1^2)^{1/2} z_0 + z} du \right] \quad (21)$$

which yields, using Eq. (20):

$$INT_2 \doteq \frac{\gamma_0^2}{\gamma_1^2} \left[\gamma_1 K_1(-\gamma_1 |z_0 + z|) - \int_0^G e^{-(u^2 + \gamma_1^2)^{1/2} z_0 + z} du \right] \quad (22)$$

But for $u \leq G$ the term $(u^2 + \gamma_1^2)^{1/2}$ is approximated by γ_1 .

$$INT_2 \doteq \frac{\gamma_0^2}{\gamma_1^2} \left[\gamma_1 K_1(\gamma_1 |z_0 + z|) - e^{-\gamma_1 |z_0 + z|} \int_0^G du \right] \quad (23)$$

Finally producing a solution:

$$INT_2 \doteq \frac{\gamma_0^2}{\gamma_1} K_1(\gamma_1 |z_0 + z|) - \frac{\gamma_0^2}{\gamma_1^2} G e^{-\gamma_1 |z_0 + z|} \quad (24)$$

Combining Eq. (6), (15) and (24) produces an approximate solution of:

$$\Pi_{mx} \doteq \frac{IA}{4\pi} \left[\frac{e^{-\gamma_1 |z_0 - z|}}{|z_0 - z|} - \frac{e^{-\gamma_1 |z_0 + z|}}{|z_0 + z|} + 2 \frac{\gamma_0^2}{\gamma_1} K_1(\gamma_1 |z_0 + z|) - \frac{2\gamma_0^3}{\gamma_1^2} e^{-\gamma_1 |z_0 + z|} \right] \quad (25)$$

The magnetic field is found by applying the following to the magnetic Hertz vector given in Eq. (25).

$$\vec{H} = \nabla(\nabla \cdot \vec{\Pi}_m) - \gamma_1^2 \vec{\Pi}_m \quad (26)$$

Only the x component is nonzero, therefore:

$$H_x = -\gamma_1^2 \Pi_{mx} \quad (27)$$

$$H_x \doteq -\frac{IA \gamma_1^2}{4\pi} \left[\frac{e^{-\gamma_1 |z_0 - z|}}{|z_0 - z|} - \frac{e^{-\gamma_1 |z_0 + z|}}{|z_0 + z|} + \frac{2\gamma_0^2}{\gamma_1} K_1(\gamma_1 |z_0 + z|) - \frac{2\gamma_0^3}{\gamma_1^2} e^{-\gamma_1 |z_0 + z|} \right] \quad (28)$$

Equation (25) is the approximate solution to the magnetic Hertz vector at points located directly above or below radiating loop as shown in Fig. 1. Equation (28) is the final approximation for the resulting magnetic field.

In evaluating Eq. (28) and the following expressions it must be noted that the modified Bessel function and the exponential functions have complex arguments at an angle of $j^{1/2} = 45^\circ$. This Bessel function may be expressed as⁶:

$$K_1(j^{1/2}x) = -kei_1x + jker_1x \quad (29)$$

where kei_1 and ker_1 are Kelvin functions of order 1. Curves of these functions are shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2 - Kelvin functions

Power Coupling Between Antennas

The voltage developed in a receiving loop antenna of A_2 area and N_2 turns within a magnetic field, H_x , normal to the loop plane is:

$$V_2 = -\mu N_2 A_2 \frac{d}{dt} H_x \quad (30)$$

The time derivative of a sinusoidal time varying field is ω , therefore:

$$V_2 = -\omega \mu N_2 A_2 H_x \quad (31)$$

The power transfer between the transmitting and receiving antennas (assuming conjugate loading with negligible stray capacitance effects) is

$$\frac{P_r}{P_t} = \left(\frac{|V_2|}{|I_1|} \right)^2 \frac{1}{4 R_1 R_2} \quad (32)$$

R_1 and R_2 are the total resistance, copper losses plus radiation resistance, of the transmit and receive antenna respectively. The copper losses are frequency independent and equivalent to the wire resistance in the loop. The total resistance for a loop antenna placed in a spherical lossless cavity within a conductive medium is expressed by:

$$R = \frac{\sigma(\omega \mu A N)^2}{6\pi b} + 2N(\pi A)^{1/2} R_w \quad (33)$$

where: R_w = wire resistance (ohm/meter)

b = cavity radius (meter)

The first term in Eq. (33) is the radiation resistance developed by Wait⁷ while the second term expresses copper losses. In general the copper losses are much greater than radiation resistance at frequencies practical for communication (superconducting loop antennas will reverse this statement.)

The power coupling between antennas is found using Eq. (28) and (31) in Eq. (32) to yield:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{P_r}{P_t} = & \left[\frac{\omega \mu N_2 A_2 N_1 A_1 \gamma_1^2}{4\pi} \right]^2 \left[\frac{e^{-\gamma_1 |z_0 - z|}}{|z_0 - z|} - \frac{e^{-\gamma_1 |z_0 + z|}}{|z_0 + z|} \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{2\gamma_0^2}{\gamma_1} K_1(\gamma_1 |z_0 + z|) - \frac{2\gamma_0^3}{\gamma_1^2} e^{-\gamma_1 |z_0 + z|} \right]^2 \\ & \times \frac{1}{4R_1 R_2} \quad (34) \end{aligned}$$

An example of coupling between loops placed at 300 meter vertical separation within the earth is shown in Fig. 3. The curves show the power coupling between antennas for depth of 0, .1, 1, 10, 100 and ∞ meters for the shallow antenna with the second antenna at 300 meters greater depth for each case. A conductivity of 0.02 mhos/meter is used as typical of earth conductivity. The number of loop turns and loop areas are arbitrary and result in a multiplying factor according to Eq. (34). The copper losses in this example are assumed to be much greater than the radiation resistances.

Optimum Frequency of Power Coupling

Several observations may be made from the curves shown in Fig. 3. First, a significant improvement is gained by placing the shallow antenna just within the conductive medium. A gain of 56 dB is realized by setting z_0 at one meter depth over the surface radiating case ($z_0 = 0$). Second, the frequency of optimum coupling is less as z_0 assumes greater depths. It may be noted that at lower frequencies the curves have a positive slope of 40 dB per

decade. This results from ω^4 low frequency behavior of $(\omega \gamma_1^2)^2$ in the first bracket of Eq. (34). If z_0 is set for zero the first term within the second bracket exactly cancels the second term. The third term greatly dominates the fourth term and Eq. (34) may be approximated as:

$$\frac{P_r}{P_t} = \left[\frac{\omega \mu N_2 A_2 N_1 A_1 \gamma_1^2}{4\pi} \right]^2 \left[\frac{2\gamma_0^2}{\gamma_1} K_1(\gamma_1 |z|) \right]^2 \frac{1}{4R_1 R_2}; z_0 = 0 \quad (35)$$

Figure 3 - Coupling between vertically aligned Coplanar Loops placed in a conductive half space

By inserting the ω dependance of γ_0 and γ_1 , ω and $\omega^{1/2}$ respectively, Eq. (35) is shown to be proportional to:

$$\frac{P_r}{P_t} \propto y^{14} [K_1(\sqrt{j} y)]^2; z_0 = 0 \quad (36)$$

where: $y = (\omega \mu \sigma)^{1/2} |z|$

The maximum transfer of power occurs at the frequency at which the magnitude of Eq. (36) peaks. Knowing beforehand that the solution will result in a large argument (i.e., $y > 5$), the asymptotic approximation for the modulus of the modified Bessel function may be substituted. (This substitution produces an optimum frequency estimate about 4 percent high.)

$$\frac{P_r}{P_t} \propto y^{14} \left[\frac{e^{-y/\sqrt{2}}}{y^{1/2}} \right]^2; z_0 = 0 \quad (37)$$

Taking a derivative of Eq. (37) and setting it to zero yields:

$$y = \frac{13}{\sqrt{2}} = (\omega \mu \sigma)^{1/2} |z|$$

and the optimum frequency:

$$\omega_{opt} = \frac{(13)^2 \times 10^7}{8\pi\sigma(z)^2} ; z_0 = 0 \quad (38)$$

At large values of z_0 , the first term in the second bracket of Eq. (34) dominates and the power transfer function may be approximated by

$$\frac{P_r}{P_t} = \left[\frac{\omega\mu N_2 A_2 N_1 A_1 \gamma_1^2}{4\pi} \right]^2 \left[\frac{e^{-\gamma_1 |z_0 - z|}}{|z_0 - z|} \right]^2 \frac{1}{4R_1 R_2} \quad (39)$$

which is proportional to

$$\frac{P_r}{P_t} \propto y^8 [e^{-y}]^2 \quad (40)$$

where:

$$y = \left[\frac{\omega\mu\sigma}{2} \right]^{1/2} |z_0 - z| \quad (41)$$

The derivative of Eq. (40) is equal to zero at $y = 4$ which yields:

$$\omega_{opt} = \frac{8 \times 10^7}{\pi\sigma(z_0 - z)^2} ; \text{large } z_0 \quad (42)$$

By substituting Eqs. (38) and (42) into Eqs. (35) and (39) along with the expression for copper losses from Eq. (33), the transmission losses at optimum frequency for the two cases discussed are reduced to:

$$\left[\frac{P_r}{P_t} \right]_{\omega_{opt}} = \frac{3.65 \times 10^{-7} N_1 N_2 (A_1 A_2)^{3/2}}{(R_w)^2 \sigma^6 z^{14}} ; z_0 = 0 \quad (43)$$

and for large z_0 :

$$\left[\frac{P_r}{P_t} \right]_{\omega_{opt}} = \frac{4.43 \times 10^{-2} N_1 N_2 (A_1 A_2)^{3/2}}{(R_w)^2 \sigma^2 (z_0 - z)^{10}} ; \text{large } z_0 \quad (44)$$

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